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Title: APPLICATION OF ON-LINE NIR SPECTROSCOPY AND OTHER PROCESS ANALYTICAL TECHNOLOGY TOOLS TO THE CHARACTERIZATION OF SOY SAUCE DESALTING BY ELECTRODIALYSIS

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Abstract: Application of Quality by Design (QbD) approaches to food processes requires the development and identification of complex mathematical models. With reference to soy sauce desalting by electrodialysis (ED), the aim of this work was to combine several PAT tools, such as Near Infrared spectroscopy (NIR), level and conductivity probes, and a control strategy of the electric current generator, to increase the amount of information of single desalting experiments for ED modelling. Soy sauce volume and electric conductivity as well as the electric voltage and current applied to the ED stack were precisely measured at high sampling rates. NIR models of the main soy sauce physicochemical properties (density, osmotic pressure, electric conductivity; salt and non-salt solid concentrations), needed for ED modelling, were developed and applied to several experiments resulting in good predictions. Overall, the approach proposed appears useful in ED process characterization for desalting of soy sauce or other food systems.

HIGHLIGHTS

- Continuous measurement of sauce volume, conductivity and voltage was performed
- Time varying electric currents were used to control the electro dialysis stack
- Accurate NIR models were obtained for the main sauce physicochemical properties
- An in-depth characterization of soy sauce desalting by electro dialysis was obtained

1 **APPLICATION OF ON-LINE NIR SPECTROSCOPY AND OTHER PROCESS**
2 **ANALYTICAL TECHNOLOGY TOOLS TO THE CHARACTERIZATION OF**
3 **SOY SAUCE DESALTING BY ELECTRODIALYSIS**

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25 **ABSTRACT**

26 Application of Quality by Design (QbD) approaches to food processes requires
27 the development and identification of complex mathematical models. With reference to
28 soy sauce desalting by electrodialysis (ED), the aim of this work was to combine several
29 PAT tools, such as Near Infrared spectroscopy (NIR), level and conductivity probes,
30 and a control strategy of the electric current generator, to increase the amount of
31 information of single desalting experiments for ED modelling. Soy sauce volume and
32 electric conductivity as well as the electric voltage and current applied to the ED stack
33 were precisely measured at high sampling rates. NIR models of the main soy sauce
34 physicochemical properties (density, osmotic pressure, electric conductivity; salt and
35 non-salt solid concentrations), needed for ED modelling, were developed and applied to
36 several experiments resulting in good predictions. Overall, the approach proposed
37 appears useful in ED process characterization for desalting of soy sauce or other food
38 systems.

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50 **1.0 INTRODUCTION**

51 Process Analytical Technology (PAT) is a system for designing, analysing and
52 controlling manufacturing processes, introduced for the pharmaceutical sector in 2004
53 by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA, 2004) (Chew and Sharratt, 2010;
54 Grassi and Alamprese, 2018). PAT implementation in the food sector is possible thanks
55 to the fact that food processing is gradually moving from inferential monitoring and
56 control (i.e. temperature, pressure, volume, etc.) toward measuring core parameters (i.e.
57 concentrations and physico/bio-chemical profiles) in real-time. PAT in food industry
58 inspired the shift of paradigm to a Quality-by-design (QbD) approach, i.e. a systematic
59 approach that emphasizes: (i) product and process understanding, (ii) real-time process
60 monitoring and control, and (iii) continuous learning about food materials and process
61 dynamics (Grassi and Alamprese, 2018). QbD led to the transition from a feedback
62 approach (i.e. post-production quality testing) to a model-predictive approach, which
63 involves data collection through in-/at-/on-line analytical techniques coupled to key
64 technologies in PAT (van den Berg et al., 2013). However, implementing PAT and QbD
65 in food industry, and thus modelling of food processing, may be a relative challenging,
66 dynamic and multidisciplinary task due to the heterogeneous nature of food matrix,
67 complexity of processes and scale of production. In fact, model may contain numerous
68 parameters and in-/output variables (i.e. chemical, biological and physical information)
69 that must be mastered for a successful model implementation. In fact, once developed,
70 models must be identified, which means that their parameters must be estimated, and
71 this may require numerous experiments where the input and output variables need to be
72 measured precisely in complex matrices. Consequently, while QbD definitively

73 represents a great benefit in food process modelling and characterization, new
74 approaches that use the continuous measurement of core quality parameters, increasing
75 the amount of information extracted from single experiments and thus reducing the
76 number of experiments for model identification, are needed.

77 In this context, sensors using non-contact optical (e.g. computer vision or
78 spectroscopy) are optimal devices for real-time analysis of food processes (Moscetti et
79 al., 2016; Vann et al., 2017). NIR spectroscopy, in particular, is able to simultaneously
80 determine several components and properties of food systems (i.e. chemical
81 composition and microstructure) and is one of the predominant e-sensing technologies
82 used in PAT (Grassi and Alamprese, 2018; Moscetti et al., 2018, 2017; Raponi et al.,
83 2017).

84 Among food matrices, soy sauce is suitable for physicochemical characterization
85 by NIR spectroscopy (Hu et al., 2018; Iizuka and Aishima, 1997, 1999, Ouyang et al.,
86 2012, 2013) and its production process can be improved through QbD. Soy sauce is a
87 traditional condiment largely used in the Far East (Fidaleo et al., 2012) which contains
88 16-20% (w/v) of NaCl. Because of health risks related to the consumption of high-salt
89 food, NaCl content of soy sauce should be at least lowered to 5–10% (w/v).
90 Electrodialysis (ED), a unit operation for separation or concentration of ions in solutions
91 based on their selective electromigration through semi-permeable membranes under the
92 influence of a potential gradient with numerous applications in the food field (Fidaleo
93 and Moresi, 2006a), is currently claimed as a successful process for soy sauce desalting.
94 It allows to obtain 75%-desalted soy sauce with 16.5% amino nitrogen loss and no
95 deterioration in flavour, colour or taste (Fidaleo et al., 2013, 2012).

96 The complexity of models for the description of the abovementioned ED
97 processes is such that an extensive experimentation is required for a statistically sound
98 estimation of relevant model parameters. In a previous study (Fidaleo and Moresi,
99 2005b), a mathematical model for ED was used in combination with an experimental
100 procedure consisting of five sets of experiments. This model proved adequate in order to
101 model the ED desalting of several univalent (Fidaleo and Moresi, 2006b, 2005a, 2004),
102 divalent (Fidaleo and Moresi, 2010) and trivalent (Fidaleo and Moresi, 2013)
103 electrolytes. The abovementioned experimental procedure was later simplified to assess
104 only the engineering parameters that control ED desalination, and later applied to
105 concentrated brines (Fidaleo and Moresi, 2011) and soy sauce desalting by ED (Fidaleo
106 et al., 2013). To minimise the number of trials and resources required for model
107 identification of the above ED systems (that is ED of liquids highly concentrated in
108 NaCl solutions), Galvanin et al. (2016) proposed a model-based design of experiments
109 (MBDoE) approach. Optimally designed batch ED experiments involve the
110 determination of appropriate time profile for the current intensity, initial concentrations
111 and volumes.

112 The aim of this work was to develop a QbD strategy for ED desalination of soy
113 sauce through PAT-enabled technologies such as NIR spectroscopy, and level and
114 conductivity measurement devices, coupled to the control of the electric current
115 generator with preset time profiles of electric current. The proposed approach may
116 increase the amount and quality of information that can be extracted from single
117 desalting experiments making the method proposed by Galvanin et al. (2016) suitable
118 for modelling of desalting of food systems, such soy sauce or other natural seasonings.

119 **2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS**

120 **2.1 Raw materials**

121 Raw soy sauce (trade name #00642 Premium Soy Sauce PTN), manufactured by
122 Kikkoman International Inc. (San Francisco, CA, USA) and provided in about 5-gallon
123 containers (approx. 18.93 dm³) with the following nominal characteristics was used:
124 moisture, 68.6 % w/w; NaCl, 13.5-14.1 % w/w; raw protein (as N × 6.25), 9.3-9.9 %
125 w/w; carbohydrates including fibres, 6.4 % w/w; ethanol, 2.4 % w/w; ash, 15.6 % w/w;
126 pH 4.5-5.0. Sodium chloride and sodium hydroxide as well as hydrochloride acid and
127 formaldehyde solutions were of analytical grade.

128 **2.2 Process unit, data acquisition, monitor and control system**

129 *2.2.1 Process unit (the electro dialysis system)*

130 A laboratory-scale electro dialyser mod. EUR2 (Eurodia Industrie SA, Wissous,
131 France) was used (Figure 1). The ED stack was composed of 9 cation- (mod. Neosepta
132 CMX-Sb) and 8 anion- (mod. Neosepta AMX-Sb) exchange membranes (Tokuyama
133 Soda Co, Tokyo, Japan). More details about the electro dialyser were reported
134 previously (Fidaleo et al., 2013).

135 The ED stack was connected to a direct current (DC) generator mod. N5767A
136 (Agilent Technologies Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA) that could supply voltage (E) and
137 current (I) in the ranges of 0-60 V and 0-25 A, respectively.

138 Both dilute and concentrate were stocked into two 1.6-dm³ PVC tanks (i.e. C and
139 D tanks, respectively), while the electrode rinsing solution (ERS) into a 2-dm³ PVC
140 tank. They were re-circulated through the ED stack by the means of 3 polypropylene
141 centrifugal pumps. Both C and D tanks were equipped with a 2-m high graduated
142 Plexiglas tube to precisely assess variations in their volume. The C, D and ERS
143 recirculation flow rates (Q) were manually regulated by means of ball valves and flow

144 meters. Gauges for pressure (P) measurement were installed in the C, D and ERS lines
145 at the inlet of the ED stack.

146 In addition, the ED system was equipped with a circulation loop connected to a
147 peristaltic pump (a Masterflex L/S precision variable-speed drive mod. 7520-40 with a
148 Masterflex pump head mod. 7518-10; Cole- Parmer North America, USA) that
149 maintained the flow rate at $98 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$. The loop was designed to allow (i) flow-
150 through measurements (i.e. on-line scans) using sensors embedded into a series of flow-
151 through vessels mod. D01/T (WTW, Germany) and (ii) sample withdrawing of the
152 desalting soy sauce.

153 The process temperature was controlled to 20°C by a cryothermostat mod.
154 ProLine RP845 (Lauda, Lauda-Kunigshofen, Germany) equipped with a temperature
155 probe inserted into the ERS tank.

156 *2.2.2 Sensors embedded in the ED system*

157 Transflectance spectra were acquired using a Luminar 5030 Acousto-Optic
158 Tunable Filter-Near Infrared Analyzer (range 1100-2300 nm, 2-nm resolution, InGaAs
159 detector, 60-msec integration time) coupled with the bundled ‘SNAP! 2.04’ software
160 and equipped with a liquid transflectance probe mod. 731-09 (Brimrose Corp.,
161 Baltimore, USA) as described by Moscetti et al. (2013). Spectra were automatically
162 scanned and monitored every ~ 4 sec using an ad-hoc SNAP! software macro, which
163 was developed in conjunction with the ‘EMEA Spectrometer division’ of the Brimrose
164 Corp.

165 Volume (V) of the C tank was measured using a calibrated ultrasonic distance
166 sensor mod. ToughSonic 14 (Senix Corporation, VT, USA), mounted at the top opening
167 of the graduated Plexiglas tube.

168 Electric conductivity (κ) and temperature (T) of the solutions flowing out of the D
169 and C tanks were assessed using two continuous cell-flow units mod. Tetracon DU/T
170 respectively connected to a conductivity meter mod. Inolab Cond Level 1 and multi-
171 parameter instrument mod. Inolab pH/Cond 740 (WTW, Germany). Both κ and T of the
172 solution flowing out of the ERS were acquired using a discontinuous cell mod. Tetracon
173 325, fitted on-line and connected to another conductivity meter mod. Inolab Cond Level
174 1 (WTW, Germany).

175 pH and temperature (T) of the soy sauce flowing in the circulation loop were
176 measured using a probe mod. SenTix81 PLUS (WTW, Germany) connected to the
177 multiparameter instrument.

178 *2.2.3 Monitoring and control process unit*

179 The ED plant was monitored and controlled through an ad-hoc LabVIEW 2015
180 (National Instruments Corporation, USA) user interface (UI). The UI allowed (i) to
181 control the DC generator; (ii) to monitor and store measurements performed through the
182 on-line sensors; and (iii) to manually enter and synchronize the off-line measurements
183 with on-line acquisitions. On-line sensors were connected via a Universal Serial Bus
184 (USB); acquisitions were performed at the desired frequency (maximum of 1 Hz, equal
185 to 1 scan per second). In addition, the LabVIEW application allowed to pilot the
186 generator with user-controlled time-varying signals of current or voltage.

187 *2.3 Sample characterization through wet chemistry*

188 In addition to during-process measurements, soy sauce composition was
189 characterized through chemical and physicochemical off-line determinations on samples
190 taken during ED desalting (Table 1). Specifically, water activity (a_w), density (ρ), total
191 soluble solids (TSS) and transmittance spectra were measured using an AquaLab CX-3

192 instrument (Decagon Devices Inc., Hopkins Court Pullman, WA, USA), a 20-cm³
193 pycnometer, a digital refractometer (Hanna Instruments, Woonsocket, RI, USA), and
194 the AOTF-NIR instrument, respectively.

195 Electric conductivity (κ) and pH were both measured by using a multiparameter
196 instrument mod. Inolab pH/Cond 740 (WTW, Germany).

197 Concentration of sodium chloride (C_B) was indirectly determined by using a
198 chloride-ion selective electrode (Mettler-Toledo S.p.A., Novate Milanese, Italy) and
199 either $Al_2(SO_4)_3$ 0.9 M or KNO_3 1 M as ionic strength adjustors.

200 Total solids (TS) were determined by oven drying at 105 °C for 120 h.

201 Amino nitrogen content (C_{AN}) was determined as described elsewhere (Luo et al.,
202 2009) and expressed as nitrogen equivalent.

203 **2.4. Experimental procedure and operating conditions**

204 *2.4.1 ED stack cleaning-in-place (CIP) process*

205 Before the first use of the ED plant with soy sauce, membranes were cleaned by
206 performing a series of 20-min re-circulation cycles with neutral (i.e. de-ionised water),
207 acidic (i.e. HCl at pH 1.0) and alkaline (i.e. 3 kg m⁻³ NaOH) solutions.

208 After each experiment, membranes were cleaned through re-circulation cycles
209 with de-ionised water. The CIP process was stopped when a κ value lower than 100 μS
210 cm⁻¹ was reached.

211 *2.4.2 Experimental procedure*

212 Before each experiment, the liquid from the CIP process was discarded and the
213 apparatus rinsed with deionised water. Hold-up volume for C and D tanks was estimated
214 as equal to 0.12±0.07 and 0.23±0.08 dm³, respectively. Electrode rinsing was carried
215 out by recirculating a 0.38±0.03 kmol m⁻³ NaCl solution. The C and D tanks were fed

216 with $2.13 \pm 0.1 \text{ dm}^3$ of $0.41 \pm 0.01 \text{ kmol m}^{-3}$ NaCl solution and soy sauce, respectively.
217 Such liquids were re-circulated through the ED stack and corresponding reservoir at
218 constant flow rate (i.e. $70\text{-}130 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$) up to constant electric conductivity and
219 temperature; then, the DC generator set in constant current mode was piloted with the
220 pre-set time varying signal. At the same time, automatic and manual on-line
221 measurements were started.

222 *2.4.3 Operating conditions*

223 Table 2 reports the experimental conditions for the four ED experiments, which
224 were carried out at different electric current profiles (ECP) as described below:

- 225 - trial S1 (calibration set); it was carried out at a constant ECP (CC) with an intensity
226 of 2.5 A. Sampling for wet chemistry determinations was performed by
227 withdrawing twenty-nine samples of about 25 cm^3 each, i.e. one sample every 10
228 min or 20 min;
- 229 - trial S2 (prediction set #1); the ECP was a step-function of time with an intensity of
230 0.5, 2.5 and 4.5 A and time intervals of [0, 0.5] h, [0.5, 1] h and [1, 1.5] h,
231 respectively. This profile (GC3P) was repeated every 1.5 h for a total time of 4.5 h.
232 Eleven samples of 6 cm^3 each were withdrawn, i.e. one sample every 30 min;
- 233 - trial S3 (prediction set #2); the ECP was a function given by the sum of a constant
234 equal to 2.5 A and a sine function with amplitude, period and phase shift of 2 A, 1.5
235 h and $-\pi/2$ rad, respectively. This profile (SIN) was applied for three periods up to
236 a total time of 4.5 h. Nine samples of 6 cm^3 each were withdrawn, i.e. one sample
237 every 30 min;
- 238 - trial S4 (prediction set #3); the current profile (GD2) was a step-function of the
239 time, with intensity of 4.5 and 2.5 A in the time intervals of [0, 2] and [2, 4] h,

240 respectively. Fifteen samples of 20 cm³ each were withdrawn, i.e. one sample every
241 20 min for the first two hours of experimentation and one sample every 30 min for
242 the residual trial time.

243 **2.5 Chemometrics**

244 *2.5.1 Spectral band selection*

245 The spectral band selection was performed by evaluating the repeatability of the
246 instrument through the coefficient of variation (CV) of the spectral data acquired from
247 consecutive scans of each withdrawn sample (Bazar et al., 2016).

248 *2.5.2 Spectral pre-treatments*

249 Chemometric analysis was tested for several combinations of the following
250 spectral pre-treatments in addition to Mean Centering (MC): Standard Normal Variate
251 (SNV), Multiplicative Scatter Correction (MSC), Extended Multiplicative Scatter
252 Correction (EMSC), and Savitzky-Golay first and second derivatives (D1f and D2f,
253 respectively) with a second or third order polynomial fitted over a window of five (S5),
254 seven (S7) or nine (S9) features.

255 *2.5.3 Regression model development*

256 Regression models were computed using the partial least squares (PLS) regression
257 through the SIMPLS algorithm (de Jong, 1993). Every PLS model was optimized by
258 computing a venetian blinds cross-validation with 10 data splits. The dataset S1 was
259 used as calibration set, while datasets S2, S3 and S4 were employed as real-external
260 prediction sets. Therefore, Root Mean Square Error for calibration, cross-validation and
261 prediction calculations (RMSEC, RMSECV and RMSEP, respectively) were employed
262 to select the optimal number of latent variables, evaluate the robustness of the models
263 and thus, circumvent unrealistic results (Moscetti et al., 2015). Model performances

264 were also evaluated in terms of BIAS, coefficient of determination (R^2), ratio of
265 prediction to deviation (RPD) and R_p^2 (Goodarzi et al., 2013).

266 *2.6 Data handling and data mining*

267 Statistical differences among the PLS models were evaluated using the one-way
268 analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the Tukey's pairwise comparison method at
269 a significance level of 5% ($P \leq 0.05$).

270 Data handling and ANOVA were both performed using R v3.4.2 software in
271 combination with 'agricolae' v1.2-4 R-packages (CRAN, 2017). Chemometrics was
272 performed using Matlab R2015a software coupled with 'pls_toolbox' v8.6.2 software
273 (Eigenvector Research Inc., WA, USA).

274 **3.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

275 *3.1 Time courses of electric voltage, concentrating solution volume and conductivity*

276 The main components or pseudo-components of soy sauce interested in ED
277 desalting are NaCl, water and non-salt solids, the latter including amino acids which
278 represent a soy sauce quality index. During ED, mainly NaCl and water migrate through
279 the membranes resulting in desalting and water loss. The non-salt components are
280 mainly retained, even though some amino nitrogen loss can occur (Fidaleo et al., 2013).
281 Nevertheless, non-salt solids concentration changes during desalination due to water
282 migration affecting soy sauce physical properties, such as conductivity, density and
283 osmotic pressure. The two mechanisms contributing to the overall transfer of NaCl or
284 water are electro-migration and diffusion (Fidaleo and Moresi, 2011). Figure 2 reports,
285 as an example, the results of the on-line measurements for the desalting trial S2 (Table
286 2). The plots reveal several interesting aspects of the process. The voltage followed the
287 same trend of the electric current (Figure 2a), with small differences in the form, which,

288 by applying the Ohm's law to the equivalent electric circuit of the ED stack (Fidaleo
289 and Moresi, 2005b) implies an approximately constant stack resistance. The
290 concentration solution volume and its electric conductivity (Figure 2b) exhibited a
291 different form compared to the electric current. The volume variation is affected mainly
292 by water migration, while the change in conductivity is affected by salt migration. In
293 this case, the discontinuity in the electric current induced a corresponding change in the
294 local slope of the curves which are evident thanks to the great precision of the
295 measurement systems. Diffusion and electromigration contributions to water and salt
296 transfer from soy sauce to the concentrating liquid affect the time courses shape of
297 volume and electric conductivity. Electromigration determines a transfer of matter from
298 the diluting to the concentrating stream and is proportional to the applied electric
299 current. Diffusion flux, on the other hand, is driven by the concentration difference
300 across the membranes and is directed to the lower concentration side of the membranes.
301 Salt concentration difference between soy sauce and the concentrating liquid is positive
302 at the beginning of the experiment, gradually decreases and finally becomes negative.
303 Thus, the salt diffusion flux is directed from the soy sauce to the concentrating liquid at
304 the beginning of the experiment, then it decreases and at the end it changes direction.
305 On the contrary, the diffusion flux of water, called electro-osmotic flux, is directed
306 always in the opposite direction of the diffusion flux of NaCl. The overall fluxes of salt
307 and water, resulting from the sum of the two abovementioned fluxes, change during the
308 desalination. In particular, the diffusion contribution changes in quantity and sign while
309 the electromigration one changes only in magnitude since it is proportional to the
310 applied electric current. In light of foregoing considerations, the patterns observed in
311 Figure 2b give insight into the contribution of diffusion and electromigration to the

312 overall flux, since the volume and conductivity curve slopes are approximately
313 proportional respectively to the water and salt flux.

314 The analysis of the electric voltage, conductivity and volume of the concentrating
315 solution allows to draw the following conclusions: (i) the electric current signal is
316 transmitted instantaneously to the system, without any lag; (ii) the stack seems to work
317 at a constant apparent electric resistance; (iii) variations induced by the electric current
318 on the other parameters (i.e. volume and conductivity) are evident and in agreement
319 with the system expected behaviour. Thus, it seems that precise information for ED
320 modelling on the stack electric behaviour and diffusive and electromigration mass
321 transfer can be extracted from the experiment.

322 In order to fully characterize a desalting process, monitoring of changes in
323 concentration of salt, non-salt solids and amino nitrogen is needed. Consequently, these
324 physicochemical characteristics (and others) were determined through prediction
325 models based on NIR spectroscopy.

326 *3.2 Descriptive statistics of reference ED parameters*

327 Table 3 reports descriptive statistics of reference data acquired off-line for the
328 four desalination experiments used to calibrate and validate PLS models capable of on-
329 line estimating analyte concentrations and physicochemical parameters (Y) from NIR
330 spectra (X). It can be noted from CV values that some variables underwent substantial
331 variations during the experiment while others did not change appreciably. Results on
332 descriptive statistics were consistent among the trials.

333 *3.3 Spectral band selection*

334 On the basis of the results obtained from the repeatability study of NIR spectra,
335 the noisy spectral region at 1926-2300 nm characterized by CV values higher than 5%
336 was removed from the operative spectral range (i.e. 1100-2300 nm). (Figure S1).

337 *3.4 Pre-treatment of NIR spectral data*

338 Comparison of NIR scans performed on-line and off-line (i.e. under static
339 conditions on samples withdrawn from the desalting soy sauce) showed apparent
340 differences in spectral profiles acquired at the same time intervals of processing. These
341 differences may be attributed to light scattering, responsible for multiplicative effects
342 because of path length variations, which was most likely due to foam or air-bubbles
343 flowing through the NIR probe during the on-line measurements. Light scattering and
344 noise presence were observed also by Zhao et al., (2013) on NIR spectra acquired on-
345 line on soy sauce. Hence, a data rescaling was a needed, and SNV, MSC and EMSC
346 spectral pre-treatments were individually tested for their effectiveness in reducing
347 scatter effects from the on-line spectra. Figure 3 shows the effect of the SNV pre-
348 treatment on the 1450-1900-nm wavelength region for desalination S1 (Table 2). In
349 detail, Figure 3a shows the raw NIR spectra acquired on-line as a function of time,
350 while Figure 3b shows how the same spectra, after pre-treatment, keep spectral profiles
351 similar as before pre-treatment but assume correct temporal trends as evidenced by the
352 6-h color ramp. The mean transfectance values measured off-line or on-line at 1664 nm
353 are reported in Figure 3c and 3d (i.e. before and after pre-treatment, respectively). This
354 spectral band, corresponding to a sharp local maximum of the transfectance, was
355 chosen as example to easily visualize the effect of the spectral pre-treatment. It can be
356 observed from Figure 3c that raw data obtained off-line show some linearity,
357 corresponding to the real trend of several physicochemical parameters measured on-line

358 for trial S1 (data not shown), even without the pre-treatment, while on-line raw data
359 present an unusual trend. In fact, Figure 3d shows the effectiveness of the spectral pre-
360 treatment in successfully aligning the on-line scans to the off-line measurements, even
361 though little differences in slope might be speculated. Consequently, spectral rescaling
362 was extremely helpful in removing scatter effects observed during on-line acquisitions
363 and then in computing more robust prediction models.

364 *3.5 PLS regression models*

365 Prediction models were calibrated on spectral data measured off-line on samples
366 withdrawn during the experiment S1 and validated on real-external datasets acquired
367 on-line during trials S2, S3 and S4 (Table 2). Reference data (i.e. physicochemical
368 properties of sample) were always acquired off-line. The complete calibration and
369 prediction performances of the regression models are summarized in Table 3. As
370 expected, model performances were totally affected by the pre-treatment used. Pre-
371 treatment methods such as SNV (for baseline correction), Savitzky-Golay smoothing
372 filter with a second order polynomial fitted over a window of seven features (for noise
373 reduction) and Mean Centering (for resolution enhancement) were selected as best
374 combination for removing/reducing unwanted background information (i.e. light
375 scattering and noise). Briefly and in general terms, it can be noted that spectral rescaling
376 (i.e. SNV) improves the quality of the models and that model statistics are good or
377 acceptable in many cases. In fact, applying the scatter correction algorithm not only
378 enhanced model performances by lowering both RMSE and BIAS of prediction (P) but
379 also improved model robustness by preventing good fitting due to chance-correlation
380 problem (i.e. by increasing the R^2_p over the threshold of 0.5, needed for an acceptable
381 model). For every parameter, models with good ($R^2 \geq 0.80$), very good ($R^2 \geq 0.90$) or

382 excellent ($R^2 \geq 0.95$) coefficient of determination were obtained when spectra were
383 rescaled. In addition, models were evaluated by the RPD statistics: $RPD \leq 1$, non-
384 reliable model; $1.0 < RPD \leq 1.4$, poor model; $1.4 < RPD \leq 2.0$, fair model; $RPD > 2.0$,
385 excellent model. RPD after pre-treatment always reaches the threshold of 2.0 (Figure 4).
386 However, some exceptions rise; in fact, (i) SNV significantly improved the pH model
387 only in terms of R^2_p , and (ii) the C_{AN} model was of low quality and appeared not
388 adequate, as confirmed by its performance metrics (i.e. low R^2 , high RMSE and high
389 Bias). The reason of this is probably related to the fact that amino nitrogen changed by a
390 small quantity during each desalination, with a coefficient of variation of the same order
391 of the one characterizing the experimental error of the measurement method (Table 1).

392 For an accurate model, points should align on a straight line with slope equal to
393 one and intercept equal to zero on predicted-vs.-measured plots, typically used to
394 validate NIR models. Figure 5 reports as example such plots for all the parameters
395 studied for the prediction trial S4, except for TSS. For many parameters the plots show
396 excellent agreement between model predictions (i.e. Y predicted) and experimental data
397 (i.e. Y measured) while for others there are some discrepancies. In any case, for most of
398 the parameters the discrepancies appear small and thus, from an engineering point of
399 view, this may be acceptable.

400 *3.6 Simulation of desalination experiments by NIR models*

401 The prediction capability of NIR models can be further assessed by comparing
402 the predicted and measured time courses of the studied parameters for the
403 prediction trials (S2, S3 and S4, Table 2) as shown in Figure 6 for the parameters
404 C_B , C_{AN} , C_{NS} , TSS and π . These plots confirm the good prediction capability of the
405 developed NIR models except for the amino nitrogen, especially in trial S4. It is

406 evident that the concentration profiles obtained by the NIR models, especially for
407 sodium chloride and non-salt solids weight concentrations (C_B and C_{NS} ,
408 respectively), present a trend that is globally decreasing or increasing, respectively,
409 with oscillations similar to the ones observed in conductivity and in concentrating
410 solution volume (Figure 2), which were measured with dedicated sensors. Such
411 oscillations are not revealed by the physicochemical properties of samples
412 measured off-line. Thus, it seems that NIR predictions can reproduce the fine
413 variations of physicochemical properties at least for the most important parameters,
414 i.e. sodium chloride and non-salt solids concentrations as well as some
415 physicochemical properties.

416 The time trend of sodium chloride, non-salt solids and amino nitrogen
417 depends on the electromigration and diffusion of soy sauce components through the
418 ED membranes. Water migrations has also an indirect effect on the concentrations
419 of the other components because it determines volume variations and thus leads to
420 concentration or dilution of the other components. Salt concentration decreases as a
421 function of time because of both electromigration and diffusion. The non-salt
422 solids, made up of different compounds such as proteins, organic acids, etc.,
423 transfer from the diluting to the concentrating liquid most likely with low diffusive
424 fluxes (Fidaleo et al., 2013). Nonetheless, non-salt solids concentration increases
425 over time in all trials (Figure 6) because of water migration from soy sauce to the
426 concentrating liquid. In the case of amino nitrogen, amino acids electro-migration
427 and concentration effect due to water migration can explain the trend observed in
428 Figure 6.

429 **4.0 CONCLUSIONS**

430 For the studied plant set up, the current intensity time functions used led to
431 variations in the parameter characterizing the system, such as the voltage applied to the
432 ED stack and the conductivity and volume of solutions, which could be measured with
433 great precision by the relative sensors mounted on-line. Furthermore, many parameters,
434 such as the salt and non-salt concentrations of the desalting soy sauce as well as its
435 physicochemical properties, such as conductivity, osmotic pressure and density, could
436 be predicted with high precision by using NIR models starting from the on-line
437 acquisition of spectral data. In particular, the developed NIR models were validated on
438 several independent desalination experiments and appeared robust for most of the
439 studied parameters. Overall, the approach used intensifies the amount of information
440 extracted from single desalting experiments and give insight into the electrical and mass
441 transfer behavior of the ED stack. Future work will be devoted to check if the data
442 collected and the NIR models developed in this work can be used to fit electro dialysis
443 models described in the literature and if their parameters can be estimated from single
444 desalination runs.

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FIGURE CAPTIONS

- Figure 1.** *Scheme of the ED system. ERS, electrode rinsing solution; P, pressure sensor; Q, volumetric flow-rate sensor; k, T, conductivity and temperature sensors, respectively; V, volumetric sensor (i.e. ultrasonic distance sensor); pH, pH sensor; NIR, near-infrared liquid transfectance probe; dashed black line, automatic acquisition; solid black line, manual acquisition.*
- Figure 2.** *Example of time course of the electric current intensity (I) and the voltage applied to the ED stack (E) (a), as well as the electric conductivity (k) and the volume (V) of the concentrate solution (b) (trial S2, Table 2).*
- Figure S1.** *Evaluation of repeatability of the NIR measurements through the coefficient of variation (CV) of the soy sauce spectrum.*
- Figure 3.** *Effect of SNV pre-treatment on the mean on-line spectral profiles for the 1450-1900-nm wavelength region (a, b) and on the trend of the mean transfectance values at 1664 nm up to 6-h electrodialysis (c, d) (trial S1).*
- Figure 4.** *Impact of spectral pre-treatments on the ratio of prediction to deviation (RPD) value for each PLS model. Mean values belonging to the same parameter without common letters are statistically different ($P \leq 0.05$); na, statistical comparison not available. $RPD \leq 1.0$, non-reliable model; $1.0 < RPD \leq 1.4$, poor model; $1.4 < RPD \leq 2.0$, fair model; $RPD > 2.0$, excellent model. a_w , water activity; TSS, total soluble solids; C_B , solute weight concentration; C_{NS} , non-salt solids weight concentration; k, electric conductivity; ρ , density; C_{AN} , amino nitrogen content; π , osmotic pressure.*
- Figure 5.** *PLS regression plots of Y-measured (reference) and Y-predicted (NIR) values for water activity (a_w), solute weight concentration (C_B), non-salt solids weight concentration (C_{NS}), amino nitrogen content (C_{AN}), osmotic pressure (π), pH, density (ρ) and electric conductivity (κ).*
- Figure 6.** *Time courses of predicted (NIR) and measured (reference) values for solute weight concentration (C_B), non-salt solids weight concentration (C_{NS}), amino nitrogen content (C_{AN}), total soluble solids (TSS) and osmotic pressure (π) for S2 (a, d), S3 (b, e) and S4 (c, f) prediction sets.*

Figure S1
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TABLE 1

	Descriptor	Symbol	Unit	Mean	St.Dev.	CV (%)	Rep.	Temp. (°C)	Type of measurement
	Electric conductivity	k	$S\ m^{-1}$	10.44	0.10	0.96	4	20	OFF-M, ON-M, ON-A
	pH	pH	-	4.49	0.06	1.34	3	20	OFF-M, ON-A
	Total soluble solids	TSS	°Brix	37.90	0.00	0.00	3	20	OFF-M
	Water activity	a_w	-	0.84	0.00	0.24	4	26	OFF-M
	Total solid concentration	C_{TS}	$kg\ m^{-3}$	350.60	12.98	3.70	4	20	OFF-M
	NaCl concentration	C_B	$kg\ m^{-3}$	164.80	4.67	2.84	3	Ambient	OFF-M
	Non-salt solids weight concentration	C_{NS}	$kg\ m^{-3}$	185.80	15.70	8.40	4	20	OFF-M
	Amino nitrogen concentration	C_{AN}	$kg\ m^{-3}$	7.80	0.40	5.13	3	Ambient	OFF-M
	Density	ρ	$kg\ m^{-3}$	1165.00	6.00	0.52	3	20	OFF-M
	Osmotic pressure	π	bar	240.50	4.00	1.70	4	20	ON-A

TABLE 2

Trial	ECP	C_{ERS} ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	Δt (h)	Tank C			Tank D		
				C_{B0} ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	V_0 (dm^3)	Q ($dm^3\ h^{-1}$)	C_{B0} ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	V_0 (dm^3)	Q ($dm^3\ h^{-1}$)
S1	CC	20.82	6.0	5.52	2.19	70	151.91	2.17	125
S2	GC3P	20.38	4.5	0.45	2.34	70	148.17	1.69	125
S3	SIN	20.53	4.5	0.65	2.21	80	143.02	1.72	130
S4	GD2	20.60	6.0	23.53	2.23	80	154.90	1.65	120

ECP, electric current intensity time profile; C_{ERS} , solute concentration of the electrode rinsing solution; Δt , duration of batch experiment; C_{B0} , initial solute weight concentration; V_0 , initial solution volume; Q , volumetric flow rate.

TABLE 3

Parameter	Trial S1 (calibration set)							Trial S2 (prediction set #1)					
	Min	Mean	Max	Range	St.Dev.	CV (%)	Min	Mean	Max	Range	St.Dev.	CV (%)	
a_w	0.86	0.91	0.96	0.10	0.03	3.23	0.86	0.91	0.95	0.08	0.03	3.08	
TSS (°brix)	24.75	28.95	34.05	9.30	2.83	9.78	24.25	28.03	33.10	8.85	2.92	10.42	
C_B ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	18.60	89.31	166.90	148.30	44.14	49.42	33.82	92.26	148.27	114.45	38.88	42.14	
C_{NS} ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	154.00	170.55	192.20	38.20	10.53	6.17	159.21	166.66	180.62	21.41	7.77	4.66	
k ($S\ m^{-1}$)	2.32	6.76	9.78	7.46	2.41	35.70	-	-	-	-	-	-	
ρ ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	1079.30	1114.69	1150.03	70.73	21.95	1.97	-	-	-	-	-	-	
C_{AN} ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	6.11	6.62	7.36	1.25	0.31	4.68	5.74	6.38	7.08	1.34	0.48	7.52	
π (bar)	52.50	123.00	201.90	149.40	43.68	35.51	69.46	122.93	191.68	122.23	41.53	33.79	
pH	4.44	4.54	4.69	0.25	0.08	1.77	4.46	4.56	4.66	0.20	0.07	1.45	
	Trial S3 (prediction set #2)							Trial S4 (prediction set #3)					
a_w	0.87	0.91	0.95	0.09	0.03	3.07	0.86	0.92	0.96	0.10	0.03	3.30	
TSS (°brix)	24.80	28.38	33.20	8.40	2.79	9.84	26.50	29.56	33.50	7.00	2.23	7.56	
C_B ($kmol\ m^{-3}$)	37.30	88.10	143.10	105.80	41.09	46.64	11.90	84.48	154.90	143.01	44.72	52.94	
C_{NS} ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	166.14	174.88	188.81	22.67	9.79	5.60	142.86	166.61	197.22	54.37	16.60	9.96	
k ($S\ m^{-1}$)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.76	6.22	10.02	8.26	2.60	41.74	
ρ ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1090.80	1121.73	1158.23	67.43	21.96	1.96	
C_{AN} ($kg\ m^{-3}$)	6.04	6.35	6.92	0.88	0.30	4.76	7.14	7.37	7.70	0.56	0.15	1.97	
π (bar)	67.32	123.68	193.24	125.93	41.93	33.90	54.57	119.99	201.86	147.29	44.92	37.44	
pH	4.52	4.60	4.72	0.20	0.07	1.46	4.41	4.59	4.79	0.38	0.11	2.37	

a_w , water activity; TSS, total soluble solids concentration; C_B , solute weight concentration; C_{NS} , non-salt solids weight concentration; k , electric conductivity; ρ , density; C_{AN} , amino nitrogen content; π , osmotic pressure; CV, coefficient of variation.

TABLE 4

Parameter	Pre-treatment			LVs	RMSE			BIAS			R ²			R ² _p	RPD				
	SC	SG	MC		C	CV	P	C	CV	P	C	CV	P						
a _w	-	7	yes	3	0.002	0.002	0.057	a	0.0E+00	-2.1E-04	4.4E-02	a	0.996	0.995	0.416	b	0.89	0.78	b
	SNV	7	yes	2	0.002	0.002	0.004	b	0.0E+00	2.2E-05	1.2E-03	b	0.995	0.994	0.995	a	0.92	10.61	a
TSS (°brix)	-	7	yes	1	2.056	2.657	5.665	a	0.0E+00	6.4E-02	-3.5E+00	b	0.462	0.298	0.710	a	0.30	0.57	b
	SNV	7	yes	3	0.146	0.176	0.843	b	7.1E-15	1.3E-02	-1.2E-02	a	0.997	0.996	0.991	a	0.82	6.72	a
C _B (kg m ⁻³)	-	7	yes	1	31.679	40.863	97.134	a	0.0E+00	9.7E-01	-6.4E+01	b	0.468	0.302	0.703	a	0.30	0.56	b
	SNV	7	yes	3	2.685	3.347	6.518	b	4.3E-14	1.2E-01	2.5E+00	a	0.996	0.994	0.986	a	0.82	8.09	a
C _{NS} (kg m ⁻³)	-	7	yes	3	2.624	3.696	28.989	a	0.0E+00	3.7E-01	2.2E+01	a	0.935	0.880	0.445	a	0.81	0.56	b
	SNV	7	yes	2	2.817	3.279	8.581	b	2.8E-14	1.5E-03	-1.9E+00	b	0.925	0.899	0.833	a	0.82	2.24	a
k (S m ⁻¹)	-	7	yes	6	0.060	0.266	0.971	a	-7.1E-15	-4.7E-02	-8.6E-01		0.999	0.988	0.969		0.48	5.50	
	SNV	7	yes	2	0.163	0.175	0.184	b	-1.4E-15	1.4E-02	-5.6E-02		0.995	0.995	0.998		0.93	14.35	
ρ (kg m ⁻³)	-	7	yes	3	1.911	2.942	40.293	a	0.0E+00	3.5E-01	-2.7E+01		0.992	0.982	0.033		0.88	0.71	
	SNV	7	yes	3	1.875	2.387	11.111	b	0.0E+00	6.3E-02	-1.1E+01		0.992	0.988	0.975		0.81	6.24	
C _{AN} (kg m ⁻³)	-	7	yes	3	0.202	0.505	3.151	a	0.0E+00	-7.9E-02	3.1E+00	a	0.564	0.022	0.583	a	0.34	0.17	b
	SNV	7	yes	2	0.104	0.109	0.301	b	0.0E+00	-1.0E-02	1.7E-01	b	0.885	0.878	0.609	a	0.77	1.56	a
π (bar)	-	7	yes	1	31.558	41.014	98.273	a	-1.4E-14	1.1E+00	-6.3E+01	b	0.458	0.288	0.727	a	0.28	0.56	b
	SNV	7	yes	3	2.930	3.665	6.885	b	0.0E+00	3.8E-01	-1.6E+00	a	0.995	0.993	0.989	a	0.82	9.60	a
pH	-	7	yes	6	0.004	0.019	0.073	a	1.8E-15	-2.4E-04	-6.3E-02	a	0.997	0.938	0.920	a	0.47	3.47	a
	SNV	7	yes	2	0.008	0.009	0.063	a	0.0E+00	-9.1E-04	-5.6E-02	a	0.991	0.988	0.948	a	0.91	3.91	a

SC, scatter correction; SG, Savitzky-Golay filter window; MC, mean centering; LVs, number of latent variables; C, calibration; CV, cross validation; P, prediction; a_w, water activity; TSS, total soluble solids; C_B, solute weight concentration; C_{NS}, non-salt solids weight concentration; k, electric conductivity; ρ, density; C_{AN}, amino nitrogen content; π, osmotic pressure

TABLE CAPTIONS

Table 1. Chemical and physicochemical characterization of the raw soy sauce used for the ED desalting experiments. The column 'Type of measurement' refers to how descriptors were acquired during each ED experiment, i.e. manually (M) and/or automatically (A) measured through on-line (ON) and/or off-line (OFF) methods.

Table 2. Outline of the experimental conditions for the ED desalting experiments.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for the reference (off-line) measurements in calibration and prediction sets. Electric conductivity (k) and density (ρ) parameters were only measured during trials S1 and S4.

Table 4. Summary of performance metrics of the best PLS regression models for both non-pre-treated and pre-treated spectra. Different letters indicate significant differences (P<0.05) between models within the same parameter. ANOVA was not performed for the BIAS, R² and RPD metrics of the k and ρ parameters because model validation was performed using the S4 prediction set only.